

STUDENTS' RELIANCE ON AI TOOLS IN EFL COURSES IN HIGHER EDUCATION: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract

In recent years, use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is becoming increasingly popular among university students who are learning English Language. Furthermore, it addresses concerns regarding the potential for students to become overly dependent on AI applications in their language learning. It is important to ensure that technology serves as a tool to enhance learning, rather than a substitute for fundamental skills. While AI is increasingly taking on various roles in education, there has been limited research work examining students' attitudes, perceptions towards its use, especially in the context of English as a Foreign Language (EFL).

This study aimed to identify students' views on current usages of AI powered tools, and its advantages and disadvantages of using AI in English learning, it included 211 students from anonymous university in Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia. The questionnaire was developed and distributed by using Microsoft forms. Based on data results of both open & close ended questions, this study employed a mixed-method approach integrating qualitative and quantitative research analysis. The research results indicate that students recognize the potential risks of over-relying on AI, particularly its adverse impact on their productive skills. They noted that AI often provides unreliable responses and expressed that they have not been educated on the ethical aspects of AI, emphasizing the necessity for more guidelines in utilizing AI for learning English. Moreover, the study emphasizes the significance of incorporating balanced integration to prevent reliance on AI in language education,

Keywords: tertiary level EFL students; dependence on AI generated tools, concerns, students' views, learners' autonomy.

1. Introduction

Education systems worldwide are shifting toward in the direction of a more customized, technology enhanced, and student-centered curriculum. One of the latest technological developments artificial intelligences has attracted people all across the world, generating intense discussion, particularly in Education (Dr Adam Edmett, 2024). Artificial intelligence (AI) is the capability of computer systems to accomplish tasks that generally require human intelligence, such as learning, reasoning, problem-solving, decision-making, and perception, and contemporary explanations are varied (Khawlah M. Al-Tkayneh, 2023). The development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in 1956 was a significant moment in technology. Newell and Simon created a program called the "thinking machine," which aimed to replicate human thinking skills for solving complex problems. This innovation set the stage for the development of AI in Education, a domain focused on utilizing AI technologies to transform teaching, learning, and decision-making processes (Budi Waluyo, 2024). Although artificial intelligence provides innovative solutions in various fields, many individuals still find learning foreign languages challenging. Factors such as lack of motivation, difficulties with language structures, and limited practice time often hinder them from reaching their language objectives.

The integration of AI in education raises some concerns that require a deliberate approach (Aljabr, 2024). What impact will AI have on student learning and skill development? Fraidan (2025) reported that AI has the potential to enhance education by personalizing learning. However, challenges include potential biases and risks to critical thinking and originality. It's vital to integrate AI carefully alongside traditional methods,

guiding students in using AI-generated feedback effectively. According to (Nagaletchimee Annamalai, 2025) advancements in AI and its use in education have raised important ethical issues. The decision by esteemed institutions, including Oxford and Cambridge, which are members of the UK's Russell Group, to implement stringent measures that restrict the use of generative AI in academic programs—due to concerns regarding academic integrity—further emphasizes the need for thorough and comprehensive research in this area. Thus, understanding students' attitudes is essential, as it reveals how they perceive and utilize technology in their learning process (Rosmayanti, 2024).

2. Research objectives:

The current study aims to:

- Evaluate the students' perceptions about using AI in EFL learning
- Explore students' use of AI tools in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learning, their potential over-reliance
- Find-out further pedagogical implications for using AI in EFL

3. Literature Review

Previous research findings indicate that AI tools possess the ability to revolutionize the English language learning experience by personalizing, streamlining, and enhancing flexibility. Vivit Rosmayanti (2024) highlighted the following challenges and concerns in AI tools such as: Over-reliance on AI Tools, Limited Understanding of Tool Functions, Concerns about Academic Integrity, Difficulty in Adapting to AI Usage, Accuracy of AI-generated Responses. According to this paper a significant concern among students is the reliance on AI tools, which may prevent them from developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

They also question the reliability of AI responses, particularly with tools like ChatGPT that can provide misleading information. Moreover, there are worries about academic integrity, especially regarding the use of AI for essay writing and ethical implications. These issues complicate the balance between developing AI skills and maintaining academic honesty, as dependence on AI for grammar and structure can hinder creativity. Similarly, scholars Arthur and others (2024) emphasized that an overreliance on technology can present significant risks. When trust in artificial intelligence is excessively high, users may inadvertently overlook critical errors and act on recommendations that could be detrimental to themselves and others. Moreover, Aina Al Mardhia Ismail (2024) carried out research aimed at examining the issue of excessive dependence on AI tools in academic writing tasks among Malaysian university students. The results revealed that Malaysian undergraduates frequently utilize AI tools for tasks such as translation, content creation, grammar and spelling checks, as well as plagiarism detection. This dependence is driven by easy access to technology, insufficient writing skills, academic pressures, and limited proficiency in English as a second language. The study suggests that educators should assist students in using AI tools to encourage critical thinking and promote responsible and ethical use of technology. Similarly, Yang Aijun (2024) demonstrated that AI translation tools and learning platforms may cause learners to become too reliant on technology. These resources quickly address language issues and provide ready-made answers. While they seem to enhance efficiency, they can ultimately weaken learners' ability to solve problems independently and engage in deeper learning. For instance, when facing basic language structure issues, students may choose to use translation tools instead of solving problems through their own reasoning. This approach deprives them of the valuable learning that occurs from attempting, failing, and reflecting, which can hinder their development of foreign language thinking skills. Additionally, Ahmer Rauf (2025) and others discussed that while AI tools enhance efficiency, they may challenge originality and independent problem-solving skills. The study highlights that structured teacher interventions, ethical AI guidelines, and innovative assessments can allow AI to complement the learning process, fostering independent and creative learners while maintaining the integrity of L2 education. According to Al-Mashaqba as cited in Khawlah the integration of artificial intelligence could bring forth critical issues about how decisions are made and the level of human participation in the education system. Furthermore, there are considerable worries about the confidentiality and safety of student information used to develop AI models, as well as the possibility of diminishing in-person teaching, which may lead to reduced social engagement and long-term isolation (Khawlah M. Al-Tkhayneh, 2023). Furthermore, Nadjiba Merdass (2024) highlights the negative impacts of overreliance on AI on student creativity and academic performance, suggesting solutions to mitigate

misuse, and emphasizes the need for thorough strategies to minimize these risks, ensuring technology remains a helpful tool rather than a barrier.

4. Challenges & Policy Implications in Education:

UNESCO (07, 2019) highlights the various challenges and policy considerations that must be incorporated into both global and local dialogues regarding the advantages and risks associated with integrating AI into education and preparing students for an AI-driven environment. The first challenge involves the creation of a comprehensive public policy on AI aimed at sustainable development, which necessitates the coordination of multiple factors and institutions. The second challenge is to promote inclusion and equity in AI applications within education. Tackling issues such as insufficient technological infrastructure is essential for executing strategies that utilize AI to enhance learning experiences. The third challenge pertains to equipping teachers with the necessary skills for AI-integrated education. The fourth challenge is the establishment of robust data systems to support education, underscoring the importance of better data collection and management practices. The fifth challenge is to amplify the influence of AI-related educational research, recognizing earlier challenges in bridging research findings with practical applications and policy formulation. The sixth challenge centers on ethical considerations and transparency in data usage, highlighting the need for public discussions on ethical concerns and accountability within AI practices.

Faisal Rehman Channa (2021; Vol 20 (Issue 5)) claimed that to prepare today's youth for the AI future, we must utilize AIED effectively while addressing its limitations and ethics. We should integrate AI tools and innovative teaching methods to foster collaboration, creativity, and essential 21st-century skills. Transforming education with action-oriented strategies will empower students and enhance their skill development.

5. Concerns of integrating Artificial Intelligence in EFL learning:

According to report by British Council (2024) "Artificial Intelligence and English Language Teaching: Preparing for the future" AI presents challenges for English Language Teaching (ELT), including four main areas as: 1. technology breakdowns: issues with technology encompassed both technical failures and inadequate connectivity. A notable example of a technology failure involved the AI providing incorrect responses. 2. Limited capabilities: Some users desired more sophisticated features. For example, certain learners were looking for improved chatbot capabilities, while others sought more natural interactions. These restricted functionalities resulted in learners losing interest in using the chatbot. 3. Fear: arose from sharing of personal information, ambiguity about AI operation, and loss of a natural learning environment along with emotions. The initial concern revolved around sharing personal information due to uncertainty about data storage and access. Additionally, a perception study revealed that students feared a loss of natural environments and genuine emotions when engaging with AI. 4. Standardizing languages and ideology: Google may

reinforce the use of standardized language. If it is trained primarily on samples of spoken English from countries where English is widely spoken or where many are learning it, there may be variations of English or pronunciations that are not included in its database. These variations may be easily understood by others but could be marked as inadequate because they don't appear in the dataset. A learner who used the tool discovered that Tagalog was not recognized as a language by Google Translate, and the only option available for the Tagalog-speaking student translating her own language to English was Filipino, which has been the recognized standardized language of the Philippines since 1987 (2024).

Establishing clear ethical standards and data privacy measures could foster trust and promote the responsible use of AI in English Language Teaching

(ELT). Educators should remain aware of the limitations of AI and approach its excitement with caution. In general, the concerns associated with AI in ELT are frequently ignored, highlighting the need for increased focus on recognizing and tackling these challenges (Dr Adam Edmett, 2024).

6. Data Collection and Methods:

The survey engaged a total of 211 participants from an anonymous university during the second semester of the 2024-2025 academic year. The research explored the perspectives of students on the use of AI in learning the English language. The questionnaire was made up of 13 close-ended, 2 open-ended questions.

7. Findings:

Figure 1 Students' classification

Figure 2 Level of English proficiency

It can be seen from the figure 1, The student population consisted primarily of sophomores (32%), followed by freshmen (25%), part-time Saturday students (16%), seniors (15%), and lastly, juniors (12%). Regarding English proficiency as shown in the figure 2, 57% of respondents identified as intermediate, 35% as beginner, and 8% as advanced. Most of the students identified themselves as belong to "Intermediate level".

Figure 3 summarizes the students' frequency of the AI tools usages in their English courses. As we can see 47% of them responded that they sometimes use AI, while 32% of the them said they often use them. 5% of respondents reported that they always use AI tool in their study. Just 1% of respondents said they have never used AI tools in learning of English language.

Figure 3 Frequency of the AI usages

Figure 4 Main AI tools for ESL learning

In general, several AI technologies have gained popularity among our undergraduates for the usages in various elements of ESL study. ChatGPT (30%) is a popular AI helper for a variety of uses. Next, Google Translate (29%) is a multilingual neural machine translation application that allows learners to translate texts into their mother language. 10-11% of respondents indicated they use various AI tools, like Gemini, to help

them with writing, brainstorming, learning, and other tasks. 9% of students utilized Deep Seek which is a comprehensive reinforcement learning method aimed at reasoning tasks. 8% of students use Grammarly, a cloud-based helper that examines English texts for the errors and suggests changes. Quill Bot and Claude AI were the two least used AI tools.

Figure 5 Students' use of AI for various tasks

According to figure 5, 20% of students commonly use Google Translate (GT) to translate texts. This indicates that students mostly rely on translating. 14% of respondents said they utilize AI technologies to discover new phrases or words. Similarly, 13% of participants claim to use AI tools to generate ideas and seek aid with their academic writing performances. More than 10% agreed to employ AI tools for reading comprehension. It implies that students apply AI tools in a variety of situations.

Figure 6 depicts students' self-assessments of their AI skills for the purpose of improving their English proficiency. It revealed that 49% of respondents reported having an average degree of AI literacy for language acquisition skills. 34% of participants believed they had gained good knowledge and abilities in AI-powered apps. Only 5% of them described their AI literacy as "excellent". It demonstrates that students require explicit advice and suggestions for enhancing both their AI literacy and their English proficiency.

Figure 6 Students' self-evaluation of AI skills for improving their language skills

Figure 7 illustrates the students' positions to assess themselves whether they believe AI tools make them less independent in language learning. More than 50% agreed neutrally, indicating they are aware of becoming nearly dependent on AI but they are not sure how to use it properly. 21% the participants admitted to becoming

dependent on AI tools, however, another 21% of them disagreed with the notion that AI tools reduce their independent in language learning. Just 2% answered "they strongly disagree" with the statement. That reveals those respondents believe they are using AI properly.

Figure 7 Students perception of the AI effects on language skills

Figure 8 depicts whether students agree with statement that relying on AI technologies have affected their writing skills negatively. 46% of the respondents opted for "Neutral" which implies some challenges in language learning outcome when they frequently utilized it. 24% argued that they disagree with the statement and

it can be inferred that might rely too much on AI usages. 23% of respondents agreed that AI affected badly on the learners' productive skills such as writing etc. The results of their writing might be less creative and become formulaic and generative.

Figure 8 Negative effects of AI in writing outcome

Figure 9 represents whether students agree that AI-generated translations always convey accurate meanings. 62% of them stated that sometimes they are inaccurate. When they learn English for Specific Purposes courses; for instance: Accounting; Finance etc.

there are some passages with specific professional terms and jargons that AI tools might fail to translate accurately. 5% and 16% of students stated that they are often inaccurate.

Figure 9 Inaccuracy of AI generated translations

Figure 10 describes that whether students would need more guidance on how to use AI tools ethically

and effectively in EFL learning. Majority of the respondents reported “Yes” which describes they need instructive assistance to prevent any intricacies.

Figure 10 Further guidance of AI uses

We asked the following question “Have your teachers addressed the ethical use of AI tools in your EFL classes?” 55% of students reported that their teachers gave advice on Ethical use of AI in EFL classes. However, 25% of respondents stated that teachers

never explain about proper usages of AI. Thus, teachers should explain about ethical use of AI during the classes.

Figure 11 Teachers' Advice on AI tools

65% of students agreed that AI should be completely integrated as a learning tool taking consideration of academic ethics. 29% of respondents agreed it should be used with specific guidelines. According to this viewpoint, educators must set guidelines to support responsible and ethical usage of AI, as well as offer

suggestions for successfully integrating AI into the EFL environment to benefit both teachers and students.

The other 6% of respondents stated that AI should be carefully limited, implying that students are aware of ethical concerns, issues such as data privacy and the development of critical thinking skills. They avoid of relying solely on AI for their studies.

Figure 12 Further use of AI from students' perspectives

Figure 13 shows that 35 % of the respondents admitted that reliability of the AI generated context is satisfactory which means they noticed some drawbacks of it. 34% of participants stated that "AI generated contexts are Good" which implies they are not sure about the correctness and credibility. Furthermore, 25% of

the respondents mentioned that they cannot trust AI driven answers. Only 3% emphasized that AI provides misleading, and wrong answers. These results show that students are not fully aware of its inaccurate feedback.

Figure 13 Accuracy & Reliability of AI generated context

The last two open-ended questions seek to understand students' views on the benefits and drawbacks of using AI in English learning, as well as their opinions on ethical usages. When we pose the question, "What are your opinions on the ethical and responsible use of artificial intelligence?" their responses included:

- Utilize it thoughtfully as an aid, rather than directly duplicating content.

- It is crucial to establish ethical guidelines for AI usages.

- Developing and employing AI should be done transparently, respecting human rights and ensuring data privacy.

- Generally, I tend to use it more mindfully, especially when I struggle to remember things, feel stuck, or confused; sometimes AI offers more encouragements than other sources.

- When use artificial intelligence, it is essential to check its accuracy.
- There should be a prohibition on its use.
- It is wise to use it properly to broaden one's horizons.
- Training in artificial intelligence is essential.
- Despite of the advancements brought by AI, it often fails to deliver reliable and precise information, so one should use it cautiously.

- Trust yourself and minimize reliance on AI.
- It is feasible to utilize it to a certain extent, but a complete ban is impossible.
- AI may hinder one's ability to think independently.
- I believe educators should guide students in the responsible use of AI tools.

Table below shows students' views on the benefits and drawbacks of using AI in English learning:

Table 1

Students' views	
Benefits of AI use	Drawbacks of AI
Artificial intelligence operates quickly.	AI has mistakes
Helpful in finding the information you need	cause you to feel unmotivated about handling matters on your own.
You can quickly find new words you don't know,	Artificial intelligence struggles to accurately translate contexts related to English for Specific Purposes.
You can ask AI directly instead of asking other people...	Slowing down the progress and becoming lazy in learning English
Easier, saves time	It has the disadvantage of being translated in a way that does not make sense, using words and sentences that do not fit together.
It promotes autonomous learning.	Cheating can become a habit
	Impacts on dependency mindset
	Over-reliance

Quantitative data analysis:

Table 2

Results of KMO and Barlett's Test
KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.613
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	374.087
	df	45
	Sig.	.000

To test the reliability of the research questionnaire and the representativeness of the sample size for the population, a KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) test was conducted. The result of the KMO test was 0.613, which indicates a moderate level of sampling adequacy. The significance value (Sig. or p-value) was 0.000, which is less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the variables are statistically significant and correlated with each other. In other words, the sample has an accepta-

ble level of representativeness. The highest communal-ity value was 0.815 for the question: "Do you agree that using AI negatively affects students' independent learning skills, such as translating or writing in English?" — showing that this question has the strongest relationship with the factors.

Overall, since most of the questions have communal-ity values above 0.7, the analysis confirms that the questionnaire is at an acceptable level.

Table 3

Chi-Square tests

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	37.930 ^a	8	.000
Likelihood Ratio	28.714	8	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.058	1	.810
N of Valid Cases	211		

a. 6 cells (40.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .17.

Since $p(\text{Sig}) = 0.000$ is less than 0.05, this indicates that there is a statistically significant relationship between English proficiency level and AI usage. In other words, levels in English proficiency are likely to influence the way AI is used.

In response to the question "How do you use Artificial Intelligence (AI) to improve your English skills?", 49.8% of the participants rated their usage as moderate, and 34.1% rated it as good. This shows that the usages of AI among students is relatively high.

8. Recommendations

Although AI tools can enhance language learning, their use should be balanced to prevent dependency. To promote responsible AI usage while fostering independent learning, educators can implement the following methods:

1. Encouraging Active Learning Approaches: EFL Instructors should create activities that require students to engage in critical thinking, discussion, and problem-solving rather than passively accepting AI-generated outputs. Approaches such as collaborative writing, peer feedback, and in-class debates can encourage students to develop their ideas before using AI tools.

2. Integrating AI-Aware Teaching Models; Educators can incorporate AI literacy into their curriculum, instructing students on how to assess AI-generated contents critically. Lessons on the strengths and limitations of AI can help students use these tools wisely.

3. Balancing AI with Traditional Learning Methods: A balanced approach that integrates AI tools

(Fahad S. Aljabr, 2024)

10. Conclusion:

According to the research results, 51.2% of the respondents answered that they somewhat agree and 20.4% answered that they agree with the idea that artificial intelligence reduces students' ability to learn a foreign language independently. This shows that students themselves acknowledge that AI negatively affects their independent learning skills. 46.4% of the respondents answered somewhat agree and 22.3% answered agree to the statement that using artificial intelligence negatively affects their independent learning skills, such as translating or writing in English. This indicates that students themselves acknowledge the negative impact of AI on their independent learning abilities.

The results of the study reveal that students are becoming more aware of the limitations and potential risks of relying too heavily on AI, especially regarding

alongside traditional methods such as handwritten assignments, oral presentations, and timed writing exercises can help students develop language skills independently.

4. Promoting Ethical AI Use: Teachers should establish clear guidelines for AI usage, emphasizing academic integrity and responsible digital citizenship. Schools can introduce policies that require students to disclose AI assistance in their work and use AI tools as supplementary aids rather than primary resources.

5. Developing Metacognitive Skills; Encouraging students to reflect on their learning process and evaluate their reliance on AI can foster greater self-regulation. Assignments that require students to compare AI-generated responses with their original work can highlight areas for improvement and encourage active engagement.

9. Discussion:

Fahad S. Aljabr emphasized that to promote ethical AI usage, educators should consider the importance of using AI-based plagiarism detectors for assessing students' assignments, preventing reliance on AI. Ibrahim (2023) supports this by stating that ESL teachers should utilize these tools to maintain academic integrity. Furthermore, reforming grading systems can help ensure ethical AI practices in education (Aljabr, 2024).

Future research should focus on the long-term effects of AI on language skills, strategies to overcome adaptation challenges, and effective integration of AI in different settings in both EFL teaching and learning.

their language skills. Their concerns about AI providing unreliable answers and not supporting the development of productive skills like writing could point to the need for a more structured and balanced approach to incorporating AI tools in language learning. The mention of ethical considerations is also significant—students may feel unsure about the reliability and fairness of AI-generated content, and they might be calling for more guidance in terms of how to use AI responsibly and effectively. This insight could serve as the basis for developing more comprehensive guidelines or frameworks for AI use in EFL classrooms.

References

- 07, U. W. (2019). *Artificial Intelligence in Education: Challenges and Opportunities for Sustainable Development Education Sector United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization*. UNESCO Education Sector .

2. Ahmer Rauf, A. H. (2025, January 1). MINIMIZING AI DEPENDENCY OF L2 LEARNERS FOR ACADEMIC PURPOSES: VOICES FROM EFL TEACHERS. *International journal of Social sciences bulletin*, pp. 916-921.
3. Aijun, Y. (2024). On the Influence of Artificial Intelligence on Foreign Language Learning and Suggested Learning Strategies. *International Journal of Education and Humanities (IJEH)*, pp. 107-120.
4. Aljabr, F. S. (2024). Ethical and pedagogical implications of AI in language education: An empirical study at Ha'il University. *Acta Psychologica*.
5. Artur Klingbeil *, C. G. (2024, June 25). Trust and reliance on AI—An experimental study on the extent and costs of overreliance on AI. *Computers in Human Behavior*.
6. Budi Waluyo, S. K. (2024, September 27). Generative AI in student English learning in Thai higher education: More engagement, better outcomes?
7. Dr Adam Edmett, N. I. (2024). *Artificial Intelligence and English Language Teaching: Preparing for the future*. London: British Council English Programmes.
8. Faisal Rehman Channa, D. P. (2021; Vol 20 (Issue 5)). Harnessing Artificial Intelligence in Education for Preparing Learners for the 21st Century. *Elementary Education Online*, pp. 3186-3192.
9. Fraidan, A. A. (2025). AI and Uncertain Motivation: Hidden allies that impact EFL argumentative essays using the Toulmin Model. *Acta Psychologica*.
10. Ismail, A. A. (2024). OVER-RELIANCE OF AI TOOLS IN ACADEMIC WRITING TASKS: THE MALAYSIAN TERTIARY LEVEL CONTEXT. *E-Prosiding Persidangan Antarabangsa Sains Sosial & Kemanusiaan kali ke-9 (PASAK9 2024)*, pp. 218-224.
11. Khawlah M. Al-Tkayneh, E. M. (2023, July). The Advantages and Disadvantages of Using Artificial Intelligence in Education. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, pp. 105-117.
12. Nadjiba MERDASSI, A. B. (2024, September 30). Striking the Balance of AI Use in EFL Education: Maximizing Benefits, and Minimizing Risks. *ATRAS Volume 5 (Special Issue on AI and Education, Online Learning)*, pp. 69-79.
13. Nagaletchimee Annamalai, B. B. (2025). Artificial intelligence in higher education: Modelling students' motivation for continuous use of ChatGPT based on a modified. Penang, Malaysia.
14. Rosmayanti, V. (2024, December). Students Attitudes Toward the Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools in English Language Learning. *Linguistics and English Language Teaching Journal*, pp. 285-295.